

HYDROSTATIC COMPRESSION BEHAVIOUR OF STEEL-COMPOSITE HYBRID TUBES

D. Choqueuse, B. Bigourdan, A. Deuff
IFREMER Materials & Structures group,
29280 Plouzané, France
dominique.choqueuse@ifremer.fr

B. Douchin
ICA, Toulouse University, France
bernard.douchin@iut-tlse3.fr

L. Quetel
Ste IDIL fibres optiques
lionel.quetel@idil.fr

SUMMARY

In order to promote the use of composite materials for deep offshore application, steel-composite tubes have been manufactured and tested to examine the behavior of such structures under hydrostatic pressure. The objective was to use a composite material layer to increase the safety factor of a metallic tube in order to reach a satisfactory safety limit and to significantly reduce the weight of the ensemble.

The interest of such structures under hydrostatic compression has not been clearly demonstrated, and an unexpected failure mode has been observed. Post collapse FE modeling has predicted the buckling mode of the structure but at this time the collapse pressure cannot be calculated accurately. In parallel with this study, the use of Fiber Bragg grating sensors to monitor deep underwater structures has been investigated. The possibility to use embedded sensors has been verified, and a modified interface has been developed. However, taking into account the severe loss of signal due to pressure increase, without any additional precautions the use of embedded sensors has to be limited to a pressure lower than 300 bar (3000 meters).

Keywords: Hydrostatic compression, Steel-composite hybrid tube, Fiber Bragg grating.

INTRODUCTION

Taking into account the increase of water depth in deep offshore exploitation (3000 meters) and the consequent need for lighter underwater structures, the use of composite material is of great interest [1,2]. However in order to ease the introduction of new unproven solutions in a sector where conservative solutions are preferred a study has been carried out where a mix of innovation (use of composites) and conservatism (use of steel) was developed and tested. The chosen demonstrator was a reduced scale underwater container which may represent subsea structures such as oil separators, storage tanks....

In addition, in order to improve confidence in the use of composite structures for deep sea exploitation adapted sensors are needed to monitor the behaviour of these structures throughout their lifetime (20-25 years). Together with acoustic emission and classical resistive strain gauges the use of Fiber Bragg grating embedded in the structures has been explored [3].

STRUCTURES TO BE TESTED

This study is interested in the behaviour of underwater structures for offshore applications. However, given the size of the real offshore equipment the size of the specimens tested has been limited, taking into account economical considerations and the capacity of available test equipment allowing hydrostatic loading.

The size of real equipment is about 3 meters in diameter and 10 meters long. For the study a 1/20 size model has been studied and designed for a targeted depth of 2000 meters.

The underlying approach of the design of the composite structure for offshore application is to consider that in order to promote the use of composites a step by step process involving an intermediate hybrid structure stage (steel structure - hybrid structure - composite structure) is preferable to a process consisting of replacing a steel structure directly by a composite structure.

It is therefore considered that for the hybrid structure the composite material will improve the safety by increasing the safety factor of an initial steel design with a safety factor of 1: structure type I (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Drawing of structure type I.

As hydrostatic loading (with end effect) induces a circumferential loading of twice the axial load, it was proposed to reinforce the steel structure by circumferential filament winding of carbon fibre with epoxy resin (wet process) in the central part of the specimen (structure type II). The thickness of the composite applied to the structure was arbitrarily chosen to obtain a global thickness equal to the thickness of the initial steel tube.

For this study carbon fibre has been retained, though it should be emphasized that an optimisation process of the design of such structure may lead to a different choice in terms of composite thickness and type of fibre.

The composite reinforcement has been manufactured by filament winding in the ICA Toulouse laboratory (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Manufacturing of type 2 structure.

For comparison a full thickness steel tube has also been tested (Type III).

The three types of structures studied are detailed in Table 1.

Table 1: Tube characteristics.

Type	I	II	III
Inner diameter (mm)	124	124	124
Central outer diameter (mm)	134	150	150
Steel thickness (mm)	5	5	13
Total Length (mm)	520	520	520
Composite thickness (mm)	0	8	0
Weight (kg)	12.5	14.2	23.0
Number of tests	1	5	1

The steel grade was a TU52A with following properties:

- Nominal minimal yield stress $\sigma = 345$ MPa
- Measured yield stress $\sigma = 510$ MPa

For the composite reinforcement the following components and parameters have been used:

- Type of fibre Fortafil 511 (80 000 filaments $E = 231$ GPa)
- Resin LY 5052 (Hunstman)
- Hardener HY 5052
- Curing process 15 hours at 50°C

MODELLING

Prior to testing, FE analysis of the structures has been performed. The model parameters are reported on Table 2.

Table 2: FE model parameters.

Software	Adina®
Type of elements	3D volume element 20 nodes (parabolic) for no contact zone 4 nodes for contact zone (if used)
Loading	External pressure with end effect
Edge conditions	Closures infinitively rigid
Mesh	See Figure 3 for type II

Figure 3: Mesh of type II structure.

The collapse occurred by buckling of the structure with plasticization of the steel. The results are reported on Table 3.

Table 3: FE model results.

<p>Type I 5 mm thick Steel tube</p>		<p>3 lobes mode shape Calculated collapse pressure: 400 bar Buckling then steel plasticization</p>
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Type II 5 mm steel 8 mm composite		2 lobes mode shape Calculated collapse pressure: 610 bar Steel plasticization then buckling
Type III 13 mm steel		2 lobes mode shape Calculated collapse pressure: 1000 bar Steel plasticization then buckling

FIBER GRATING INSTRUMENTATION

Long term behavior of underwater structures is governed by different parameters [4]. One of the possible failure modes is creep buckling, so strain measurements in the central part of the structures have been retained for following the long term behavior of the structure during underwater exposure. The objective is to detect the occurrence of buckling and to quantify the type and amplitude of the mode shape. Classically strain measurement is performed by resistive foil gauges bonded on the surface of the structure, but use of fiber Bragg gratings FBG is very attractive because in this case the sensor can be directly embedded in the structure during manufacturing, and it is then protected from the external environment. Extensive literature on the use of FBG's on composite materials is now available, and can be found in the following papers [5, 6, 7], however very few have studied tubes manufactured by filament winding for underwater applications, and this study offers the possibility to test the technology for this environment.

The FBG being dedicated to monitor mode shape of the cylinder, a specific sensor has been designed in order to reveal the flexural behavior of the structure. This sensor included 5 FBG's inscribed on the same fiber with a 3 cm spacing, in order to cover half the perimeter of the central part of the tube. For an expected mode 2 buckling it is necessary to cover $\frac{1}{2}$ the circumference of the central section, to be sure to cover a minimum of 1 anti node and 1 node point whatever the location around the perimeter of the section (covering of π radian angle). If mode 3 buckling is expected it is only necessary to cover a third of the circumference. The location of the fiber through the thickness of the tube is also very important. The optical sensor must be placed as far as possible from the neutral fiber of the ring in order to provide a very sensitive signal. However a minimum of cover must be retained in order to guarantee protection of the sensor from the external environment.

For this application, the multi sensor fiber has been placed between the next to last and last plies of the structure (Figure 4).

Figure 4: Location of the sensors through the thickness of the tube and placing of the sensor during the manufacturing process.

The characteristics of the multi sensor optical fiber are reported on Table 4 and Figure 5.

Table 4: Multi sensor characteristics.

Support fiber	SMF28
Coating of grated zone	No
Length of individual FBG	1 mm
Number of FBG par fiber	5
Distance between FBG	30 mm
Characteristic wavelength (nm)	1541.8 1544.56 1548.04 1550.92 1553.8

Figure 5: Reflection spectrum of the sensor.

TEST CONDITIONS

The material has been tested in the Material and Structures Laboratory of Ifremer (Brest) in a 1000 bar hyperbaric pressure tank. Seven tubes have been tested: one of type I, one of type III and five of type II. The specimens were equipped with external and internal strains gauges (12) bonded on the surface. For 3 of the type II specimens (hybrid tubes) a multi sensor FBG was placed in the central section of the tube during manufacturing. A specific underwater connection has been designed to enable the optical fiber to withstand the pressure.

During the pressure loading recording of data (strain gauge, FBG responses, and acoustic emission signal) was performed by dedicated equipment (Figure 6).

Figure 6: Test and measurement equipment.

The loading rate retained for these tests was 10 bar / min. For some tests load/unload cycles have been performed by steps of 50 bar in order to investigate damage of the structure.

BEHAVIOR OF TUBES

The results of tests are reported in Table 5.

Table 5: Results of the collapse test.

Type		Model results <i>Mode shape</i> <i>Pressure</i>	Test results <i>Mode shape</i> <i>Pressure</i>
Type I 5 mm thick Steel tube		3 lobes 400 bar	3 lobes 419 bar

Type II 5 mm steel 8 mm composite		2 lobes 610 bar	“1 lobe” 431- 517 -583 - 410 – 414 bar
Type III 13 mm steel		2 lobes 1000 bar	2 lobes 1040 bar

It can be observed that for the type I and type III structures, the steel tubes, the agreement between test results and model results is very satisfactory. The model correctly described the collapse pressure and the buckling mode of the structure. The buckling mode is initiated from the very beginning of the loading and can be detected using the strain gauges results.

For the tests on the hybrid tubes, type II, different conclusions can be drawn. All the tubes exhibited the same collapse mode, a pseudo mode 1 which has not been observed previously on metallic structures nor even on full composite tubes during hydrostatic compression. Flexible pipes can exhibit a similar buckling mode.

There is a large scatter (410 to 583 bar) between the results obtained on the different tubes which were manufactured with nominally the same conditions. No explanation (surface preparation, manufacturing and curing conditions ...) can be provided to explain the difference of behavior.

For one test (collapse at 431 bar) a debonding of the composite reinforcement from the steel pipe was observed at about 300 bar, while for the four other pipes the strain gauges indicated a load transfer between the composite and the steel parts up to the collapse. The debonded structure reached a collapse pressure which is close to the minimum collapse pressure noted for the hybrid tubes.

Subsequent to the tests, pseudo mode 1 buckling mode has been obtained by simulation by modifying the boundary condition: initial debonding of the composite part and hydrostatic pressure applied to half the surface of the debonded area (Figure 7).

Figure 7: Modelling of collapsed hybrid tube.

FBG SENSORS BEHAVIOR

One of the aims of this study was to evaluate the capability of an FBG sensor embedded in composite material to follow the strain on a structure subjected to hydrostatic pressure.

The results of strain measurements for the hybrid tube which collapsed at 517 bar are reported on Figure 8. These show the capacity of the sensor to follow the behavior of the structure up to 500 bar. However, some difficulties and losses of accuracy were observed beyond 200 bar. Nevertheless, it may be noted that the results are very similar to the results obtained with strain gauges.

Figure 8: Strain from FBG versus pressure for hybrid tube.

Figure 9: Peak FBG signal amplitude versus pressure for hybrid tube.

Analysis of the amplitudes of the reflected signals provided by the sensors indicate a strong loss of signal (-10 dB) on all the 5 FBG (Figure 9) as pressure is increased. This makes the detection of peak frequency difficult, and explains the loss of accuracy noted in the strain analysis. Strangely a subsequent increase of signal can be noted up to

450 bar. No clear explanation is currently available for this increase of amplitude but damage around the fiber of the FBG due to local stress at the micro scale of the material may be responsible. The optical fibre is very sensitive to micro bending induced during the manufacturing of the tube and this is amplified by the application of external pressure.

This may limit the use of FBG embedded in the composite without additional precaution to pressures lower than 250 bar. It should be recalled that the optical fiber was uncoated on the length in which the 5 FBG were positioned (about 20 cm).

CONCLUSIONS

A study of the behavior of hybrid composite/steel tubes under hydrostatic pressure has been performed. This shows at this stage some difficulty to predict properly the behavior of such tubes under external pressure. A beneficial contribution of external layers of composite to improve the performance of steel tube subjected to external pressure has not been demonstrated. A gain of performance, in terms of maximum pressure, of up to 50% could be obtained in some cases but large scatter in the results has been observed. An unexpected buckling mode has been noted (pseudo mode 1) and it is probable that the quality of the bonding of the composite layer onto the steel pipe strongly influences the behavior of the structure.

In addition the possibility of using FBG sensors directly embedded in the composite layer to monitor the behavior of the structure has been investigated. The use of embedded FBG's has been verified up to 200 bar external pressure. However, beyond this pressure significant decreases in performance have been noted which may indicate damage at the micro scale in the material due to external pressure. Attention must be paid to how the sensors are embedded in the material during the manufacturing process, to avoid such losses of performance.

REFERENCES

1. Chauchot P. et al, 2005, "Composite Pressure Vessels: Towards a Composite Subsea Separator", Proc. CMOO4.
2. Bigourdan B. et al., 2004, "Composite materials for subsea oil separation", Proc. DOT, Marseille.
3. Hernandez H. et al, 2009, "Entire Life Time Monitoring of Filament Wound Composite Cylinders Using Bragg Grating Sensors" (parts I, II and III) accepted in Applied Composite Materials.
4. Martin R.V. (Editor), 2008, "Ageing of composites", Woodhead publishing.
5. Ferdinand P., 1999, "Capteurs à fibres optiques à réseaux de Bragg", *Techniques de l'Ingénieur, traité Mesures et Contrôle*, R 6 735-1, in French.
6. Mülle M. et al, 2004, "Instrumented Technological Specimen (ITS): Curing process and mechanical characterization using embedded fibre Bragg gratings", Proc. ECCM 11.
7. Botsis J. et al, 2005, "Embedded fiber Bragg grating sensors for internal strain measurements in polymeric materials", *Optics and lasers in Engineering*, 43, 491-510.